

To Go Forward or Reverse: That Is Not the Question - Perspectives on the Central Dogma of Molecular Biology

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In the emerging field of gasocrinology, it is important to identify all the sources of gases that can act as signaling molecules and all the biomolecules that use gases as substrate.^{1,2} Even amino acids can act as substrates for enzymes that can synthesize gaseous molecules. Apart from *de novo* amino acid synthesis pathways, proteins that undergo degradation or lysis are also potential sources of amino acids.³ This suggests a potential reversible flow of information during the evolution of molecular life in the peptide or protein world: **Gas <-> protein**. The challenge lies in integrating this potential fact with the RNA world and peptide or protein world hypotheses, as well as the "central dogma" of molecular biology.⁴ This dogma was revised to include information occurring from **DNA <-> RNA -> protein**.⁵⁻
⁸ Thus, reversibility occurs only until RNA conversion, not from DNA or RNA to protein.

If there is one thing that is certain in biology, it's that nothing in biology is certain. Biology can only be understood from an evolutionary perspective, not based on rigid statements.⁹ For instance, viruses are an exception to the cell theory. Even in the gasocrine hypothesis, which states that *all cells require gasocrine signaling*, will eventually be proven false.¹⁰ So what about the "revised central dogma"? Will there be no *in vivo* exceptions at all? The acceptance of the "revised central dogma" hinges on the identification of a definitive "reverse translase" similar to "reverse transcriptase" in an organism. However, the absence of evidence for the irreversibility of the protein-to-RNA or DNA process (i.e., reverse translation) is not equivalent to a falsification experiment?^{11,12}

Instead of asking why reverse translation (protein to nucleic acid) cannot occur, we should ask why polymeric nucleic acids, peptides, and other biomolecules formed during evolution? Besides storing and passing information and serving a structural role, might they also serve as a form of communication? How long must be the reverse-translated sequence to falsify the "revised central dogma"? In my opinion, even if a single amino acid can be reverse-translated into a nucleic acid or converted into any other biomolecule, then the central dogma must be reconsidered. The fact that amino acids are substrates for gases that can act as signaling molecules suggests that we should reevaluate the central dogma itself. Was it a partially irreversible DNA <-> RNA -> protein process? Or was it a reversible gas <-> protein process?

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